

Chen-Wei Texts

also known as “Chen-Prophetic and Apocriphal Texts”

By Zongli Lu, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

Entry tags: Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Daoist Traditions, Religious Group, Early Chinese text, Text, Confucian Classics, Chinese Religion, Early Chinese cosmogony

The Chen-Wei Texts, or “prophetic-apocryphal” texts, refer to a corpus of religious texts that prevailed from the 1st to the 7th century C.E. in China. Chen 讖, meaning subtle and fulfilled prophecy, represents a number of esoteric writings, such as the Hetu 河圖 “Diagram of the Yellow River” and Luoshu 洛書 “Script of the Luo River.” An early appearance of Hetu in pre-Qin texts was described as precious stone or treasurable book. No later than the Warring States period, Hetu and Luoshu were commonly regarded as auspicious portents, in the form of texts with diagrams recording divination and prophecy. It was also believed that these texts sprang up from the Yellow and Luo rivers carried by mysterious animals, such as the dragon and turtle. Earlier Han (202 B.C.E.-8 C.E.) practitioners of magic methods produced a number of esoteric texts named after the Hetu and Luoshu. These texts circulated among the practitioners of magic methods (fangshi 方士) and proto-Daoists from the Third to the First centuries B.C.E. These writings covered and mixed with knowledges and concepts of astrology, geography, divination, traditional medicine, ancient myths, and witchcraft, etc. In the Earlier Han, these writings were sometimes used as prognostication books for political interests, especially when imperial legitimation and Heaven’s Mandate were under examination. A high tide of political manipulation of the chen texts took place during Wang Mang’s 王莽 usurpation of the Earlier Han and the establishment of Later Han (25-220), between 8 to 25 C.E. Once Emperor Guangwu 光武, the founding emperor of the Later Han, secured his throne, he instructed a few learned Confucian scholars to collate and purify the chen texts, ensuring that the prophetic messages were in favor of the Han imperial house. The Earlier Han Confucian teachings that had a mystical nature, such as the teachings of the Gongyang 公羊 School, the Chunqiu fanlu 春秋繁露 by Dong Zhongshu, the Jingshi Yizhuan 京氏易傳, Interpretation Associated with the Book of Change by Jing Fang 京房, and Liu Xin’s 劉歆 theories on Hongfan wuxing 洪範五行, were also merged into “prophetic interpretation” (jingchen 經讖) associated with the Confucian canons. In the last year of Emperor Guangwu’s reign (56 C.E.), an endorsed version of the prophetic texts was publicly announced. According to Zhang Heng 張衡 (78-139), a renowned astronomer and writer, the endorsed version, under the corpus title of tuchen 圖讖 “Diagram and Prophecy”, consisted of eighty one titles or volumes, including both Hetu and Luoshu and the prophetic interpretations associating with the “seven canons.” “Five Canons” and “Six Canons” were common terms used to refer to the Confucian classics in the Earlier and Later Han. “Seven Canons” occurs a few times in the Later Han materials, sometimes together with prophetic interpretations. The “Seven” indicates the Book of Change 易, the Book of History 書, the Book of Odes 詩, the Book of Rites 禮, the Book of Music 樂, the Annals 春秋, and the Book of Filial Piety 孝經 (and in some occasions the Analects 論語). Encouraged by the Later Han authorities, the learning of prophetic texts played a predominantly ideological role during the Later Han and the Three Kingdoms periods. These prophetic interpretations, which prophesized the Han House’s legitimacy to receive Heaven’s Mandate, were soon accepted as a secret canon among the Later Han Confucian schools. The two branches of the texts, the esoteric writings named after the Hetu and Luoshu, and the prophetic interpretations associated with the seven canons, although derived from different religious or intellectual origins, soon began to interact each other and mutually penetrated. In the late period of the Later Han and then after, these texts were taken as a corpus often referred to as Chen-Wei, literally “prophecy and weft” (a counterpart to Jing 經, “classic” or warp), a corpus of prophetic-apocryphal texts. Naming the prophetic interpretation texts after wei was a late Later Han phenomenon yet prevalent in post-Han eras. As a double-edged sword routinely used in socio-political struggles, established powers became vigilant about the prophecies and offensive ideas in the Chen-Wei texts. A series of bans against the Chen-Wei texts were

issued repeatedly by authorities one after another from the Third to Seventh centuries. Most parts of the Chen-Wei texts are no longer extant. From the middle of 14th to early 21st century, scholars have been working hard to collect and collate fragments of Chen-Wei and have been trying to put them together, wishing to restore the Han dynasty Chen-Wei texts to a certain extent. Dozens of Chen-Wei collections have been published. The most influential collection should be the Jushu Isho Shusei 重修緯書集成 [Revised Edition of the Collection of the Apocryphal Texts] (1971-1991) by Yasui Kôzan and Nakamura Shôhachi. However, textual problems remain in all existing collections: wrong collection, missing- collection, wrong title, wrong or missing source, suspicious source, wrong dating, etc. Currently, a research project led by Lu Zongli is in progress, attempting to re-collect and re-collate the Chen-Wei texts, which should be more accurate, more reliable and more authentic.

Date Range: 56 CE - 907 CE

Region: Han empires

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

After the short-lived Qin dynasty (221-206 BCE), the Han empires (202 BCE-220 CE) were the second set of polities that ruled over the heartland of present-day China through a unified imperial system. The Liu clan who founded the Western Han (202 BCE-7 CE) emerged from the Chu region along the Yangzi River. Around the beginning of the 1st century CE, an affinal member of the imperial family seized power and founded the Xin Dynasty (9-23 CE). After a period of civil strife, a distant member of the Liu clan eventually founded the Eastern Han (25-220) that reunified the empire. The seat of the imperial house was moved from the western capital of Chang'an (modern-day Xi'an) to the eastern capital Luoyang.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dull, Jack L. "A Historical Introduction to the Apocryphal (Ch'an Wei) Texts of the Han Dynasty." PhD dissertation, University of Washington, 1966. Ann Arbor: University microfilms.
- Source 2: Lu Zongli. Power of the Words: Chen Prophecy in Chinese Politics, AD 265-618. Oxford, Bern: Peter Lang AG, 2003.
- Source 3: Giacinto, Licia Di. "By Chance of History: The Apocrypha under the Han." PhD dissertation, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, 2007.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chen_prophecy

- Source 1 Description: An entry describes chen prophecies and their political roles in Chinese history.
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/Literature/Terms/apocryphal.html>
- Source 2 Description: An entry describes briefly the Chinese apocryphal, or wei, texts.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: Not applicable
- Source 1 Description: Not applicable
- Source 2 URL: Not applicable
- Source 2 Description: Not applicable
- Source 3 URL: Not applicable
- Source 3 Description: Not applicable

Notes: No relevant information

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: According to historical records, there were copies collected in imperial library. And there were also private collectors and literati keeping their own copies. All these copies are no longer extant since the end of 7th century C.E. There is so far no physical evidence indicating where these texts were kept.

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Notes: Written on bamboo slips or paper

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

– Wood

↳ Species

–Specify: not applicable

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: Unknown

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Materiality

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– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Notes: Written on bamboo slips or paper

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Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: There were, however, unofficial editions of the texts transmitted from the Earlier Han or created contemporaneously that were circulated among literati out of the authority's control.

– Yes

Notes: The officially endorsed edition of the texts (issued in 56 C.E.) was ideologically and financially supported by the emperor. Confucian scholars from different schools and other literati were encouraged to study this edition.

Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The authors who were responsible for the official edition were paid by the polity. And authors/copyists of unofficial editions received no payment from the polity.

- ↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
 - No
- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...
 - No
- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Present full-time?
 - No
- ↳ Present part-time?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– No

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: It was not an organized religious group, but rather an ideological system.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Notes: There are different stories narrating the origins of the texts: carried by a flying dragon or divine bird from Heaven, carried by a dragon or turtle from rivers, written by Confucius, etc.

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

Notes: In some stories, the Heavenly emperor announces oracles and bestows the texts on the chosen one.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– Yes

Notes: Such as divine birds, dragons, turtles, fishes, and water god.

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

Notes: Often in dreams, receiving the Heavenly emperor's instructions.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: Such as Confucius and Laozi.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: In the Eastern Han, only the official edition was authorized, and changes to the texts were restricted. Yet unofficial editions remained circulating via private channels, and were alterable.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: This happened after the Three Kingdoms period, when repeated bans against the Chen-Wei texts were issued and, the texts lost their authority. In a few of centuries, the texts were missing, altered, made up, etc.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: To be more specific, there was no formal institutional setting that was authorized for interpreting the texts. Instead, imperial authority and its representatives usually monopolized the discourse of interpreting the prophecies. Learned scholars interpreted the theories and concepts in the texts related to their professional fields, from ritual and musical issues, to astrological observations, and canonical teachings.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: There were always private intellectual circles that did such things.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

Notes: Quite common. Chinese prophecies were often scripted riddles containing several layers of hidden message. Interpreters often misread them until it eventually came true. Astrological observations were quite similar. As for the apocryphal part, there were also different schools or circles holding different understandings.

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Curriculum of formal education institutions in the Han were exclusively Confucianism. Nevertheless, a number of well-versed Confucian masters were also well-known for mastering the chen-wei learning. They recruited students in this field privately and openly.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Chen-Wei texts, by their mysterious nature, were full of coded messages.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Notes: Well-known commentators of the texts that time were Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 and Song Jun 宋均.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

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Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

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Is there material significance to the text?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The belief in supernatural monitoring was first described in the late Warring States Mohist writings. It then occurred in the Chen-Wei and early Daoist writings.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– No

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

–Specify: As a branch of Confucianism, the value-ethics system in Chen-Wei texts basically followed the Confucian tradition, thus supernatural beings care about behaving according to the social norms

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: A central concept in the Chen-Wei discourse was that Heaven's mandate shifts every few hundred years, thus the dynasty changes accordingly. The one who founded the new dynasty would be the messiah sanctioned by Heaven.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ Coming on a specified date

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ Coming has already passed

– Yes

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– No

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: no

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: Although no physical evidence has been found so far, it is assumed that the Chen-Wei texts contained both illustrations and writings. That should be the reason the texts were named "Diagram and Prophecy" during the Eastern Han.

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Lord of Mountain Tai 泰山 was regarded as the god in charge of dead.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

Notes: It was below this world.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Eschaton was not a common concept in Chinese traditional thought. It emerged among a few Chinese Buddhist cults in the early medieval era. In their medieval Buddhist Apocrypha, descriptions of various disasters in the Chen-Wei texts were introduced.

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

–Specify: No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Natural disasters, social disorders, human diseases, and bad fortune were all identified as punishments from supernatural powers.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: Belief in afterlife was common from the Warring States to the Eastern Han. Especially in early Daoism and later among Buddhists. But only in a few occasions can we find such beliefs in the Chen-Wei texts.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– No

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

–Specify: shorten one's life or give bad luck to one's offspring.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Both official and different private productions.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

–Specify: by content

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - No

↳ Other?
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?
– No

↳ Consists of good luck?
– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
– Yes
- ↳ Other?
– Specify: longevity of this life

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes

- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: We don't have a full picture of its calendrical design. What for sure is that from the Eastern Han to early medieval periods, court debates on calendar reform or refinement often involved citation of the Chen-Wei texts as important arguments.

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Luni-solar? (Combined, as in Mayan, Javanese, or Cham calendars)

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– Yes

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– Yes

↳ Harvest?

– Yes

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– Yes

↳ Marriage?

– Yes

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– Yes

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: not sure

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: not sure

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

↳ Pilgrimages?

– I don't know

↳ Feasting?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: This issue was discussed in association with Confucian ritual teachings.

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Yes

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god in Western Zhou China, was named Shangdi 上帝, the Supreme Emperor (Heavenly Emperor). In the Warring States period, likely influenced by the Yinyang 陰陽 Wuxing 五行 (Five Elements theory, the State of Qin introduced a Five Heavenly Emperors system, each of which was associated with an element and colour: White (Metal), Blue (Wood), Yellow (Earth), Red (Fire) and Black (Water). Their altars were allocated to different directions. The founder of the Western Han, Gaozu Emperor, inherited this system. The seventh ruler, ambitious Emperor Wu reformed and expanded the system, introduced the North Star as the supreme high Heavenly Emperor (Tianhuang dadi 天皇大帝) above all gods, and made the Five Emperors subordinate to it. In the Chen-Wei discourse, the Five Emperors took rotational turns coming down to earth, to have intercourse, physically or symbolically, with a human female and, beget a son of Heaven, who would be the founding emperor of the coming dynasty.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: In Han Empires, they were all star gods.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: In the Chen-Wei discourse, the Five Heavenly Emperors each represent one of the five powers (Wood, Fire, Earth, Metal and Water), five colors (blue, red, yellow, white, and black), five directions (east, south, central, west, and north), and five seasons and phase of life circle (Spring, to be born; Summer, growing; Peak Summer; Autumn, mature; and Winter, death).
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No

- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: The Five Heavenly Emperor each possesses one of the five (wood, fire, earth, metal, water) powers, as well as its features in color, direction, life cycle, etc.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Legends of cultural heroes and first ancestors can be found in the texts where they are regarded as spirits.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Specify: No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The belief in animism was reflected in the texts. There were named gods of almost everything, such as the eye, ear, nose, sword, shield, bow, river, mountain, and sea.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: Each of them possesses specific power that in their nature (animal, plant, water, mountain, etc.)

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?
– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?
– Yes

Notes: Because of the scattered and lost status of the texts, we are unable to restore its pantheon. However, the remaining names of gods preserved in the texts strongly support our assumption.

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization of pantheon?
 - Specify: A number of Daoist gods are mentioned in the texts.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Confucius, Laozi, Yellow Emperor 黃帝, Yao 堯, Shun 舜, Yu 禹, etc.

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?
 - Yes
- ↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: A number of folk deities are described with their names, looks, physical characteristics, in the texts.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: ghosts, animals, human organs, etc.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: astrological observation, divination in accordance with the Book of Change, Theory of the Five Elements, observation of airflow, etc.

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)
– No

↳ Divination through human communication?
– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?
– Yes

↳ Human being the interpreter of the oracle?
– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified sex/gender?
– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified ethnicity?
– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?
– No

↳ Is sex-deprivation required?
– No

↳ Are intoxicants required?
– No

↳ Is physical ordeal required?
– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?
– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?
– Other [specify]: None

↳ Other form of divination:
–Specify: Astrological observation

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?
– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?
– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?
– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?
– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?
– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?
– Yes

Notes: Although no physical evidence has been found so far, it is assumed that the Chen-Wei texts contained both illustrations and writings. That should be the reason the texts were named "Diagram and Prophecy" during the Eastern Han.

↳ Calligraphy?
– Yes

↳ Illustrations?
– Yes

↳ Illuminations?
– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Both official and different private productions.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

– Specify: by content

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: We don't have a full picture of its calendrical design. What for sure is that from the Eastern Han to early medieval periods, court debates on calendar reform or refinement often involved citation of the Chen-Wei texts as important arguments.

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Luni-solar? (Combined, as in Mayan, Javanese, or Cham calendars)

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– Yes

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– Yes

↳ Harvest?

– Yes

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– Yes

↳ Marriage?

– Yes

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– Yes

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

–Specify: not sure

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

–All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

–number: not sure

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

↳ Pilgrimages?

– I don't know

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Lord of Mountain Tai 泰山 was regarded as the god in charge of dead.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

Notes: It was below this world.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: This issue was discussed in association with Confucian ritual teachings.

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Yes

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god in Western Zhou China, was named Shangdi 上帝, the Supreme Emperor (Heavenly Emperor). In the Warring States period, likely influenced by the Yinyang 陰陽 Wuxing 五行 (Five Elements theory, the State of Qin introduced a Five Heavenly Emperors system, each of which was associated with an element and colour: White (Metal), Blue (Wood), Yellow (Earth), Red (Fire) and Black (Water). Their altars were allocated to different directions. The founder of the Western Han, Gaozu Emperor, inherited this system. The seventh ruler, ambitious Emperor Wu reformed and expanded the system, introduced the North Star as the supreme high Heavenly Emperor (Tianhuang dadi 天皇大帝) above all gods, and made the Five Emperors subordinate to it. In the Chen-Wei discourse, the Five Emperors took rotational turns coming down to earth, to have intercourse, physically or symbolically, with a human female and, beget a son of Heaven, who would be the founding emperor of the coming dynasty.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: In Han Empires, they were all star gods.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

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↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: In the Chen-Wei discourse, the Five Heavenly Emperors each represent one of the five powers (Wood, Fire, Earth, Metal and Water), five colors (blue, red, yellow, white, and black), five directions (east, south, central, west, and north), and five seasons and phase of life circle (Spring, to be born; Summer, growing; Peak Summer; Autumn, mature; and Winter, death.).

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
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- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
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- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
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- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
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- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
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- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
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 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: The Five Heavenly Emperor each possesses one of the five (wood, fire, earth, metal, water) powers, as well as its features in color, direction, life cycle, etc.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Legends of cultural heroes and first ancestors can be found in the texts where they are regarded as spirits.

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
 - Yes
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- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Specify: No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can reward
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate through other means
 - Specify: No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The belief in animism was reflected in the texts. There were named gods of almost everything, such as the eye, ear, nose, sword, shield, bow, river, mountain, and sea.

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Each of them possesses specific power that in their nature (animal, plant, water, mountain, etc.)

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: Because of the scattered and lost status of the texts, we are unable to restore its pantheon. However, the remaining names of gods preserved in the texts strongly support our assumption.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: A number of Daoist gods are mentioned in the texts.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Confucius, Laozi, Yellow Emperor 黃帝, Yao 堯, Shun 舜, Yu 禹, etc.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: A number of folk deities are described with their names, looks, physical characteristics, in the texts.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: ghosts, animals, human organs, etc.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: astrological observation, divination in accordance with the Book of Change, Theory of the Five Elements, observation of airflow, etc.

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?

– Yes

- ↳ Human being the interpreter of the oracle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified sex/gender?
 - No
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified ethnicity?
 - No
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?
 - No
- ↳ Is sex-deprivation required?
 - No
- ↳ Are intoxicants required?
 - No
- ↳ Is physical ordeal required?
 - No
- ↳ Divination through animal-behavior?
 - No
- ↳ Divination through non-living material?
 - Other [specify]: None
- ↳ Other form of divination:
 - Specify: Astrological observation

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The belief in supernatural monitoring was first described in the late Warring States Mohist writings. It then occurred in the Chen-Wei and early Daoist writings.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes

↳ Food
– No

↳ Sacred space(s)
– No

↳ Sacred object(s)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: As a branch of Confucianism, the value-ethics system in Chen-Wei texts basically followed the Confucian tradition, thus supernatural beings care about behaving according to the social norms

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Natural disasters, social disorders, human diseases, and bad fortune were all identified as punishments from supernatural powers.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: Belief in afterlife was common from the Warring States to the Eastern Han. Especially in early Daoism and later among Buddhists. But only in a few occasions can we find such beliefs in the Chen-Wei texts.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– No

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

–Specify: shorten one's life or give bad luck to one's offspring.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

–Specify: longevity of this life

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: A central concept in the Chen-Wei discourse was that Heaven's mandate shifts every few hundred years, thus the dynasty changes accordingly. The one who founded the new dynasty would be the messiah sanctioned by Heaven.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ Coming on a specified date

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ Coming has already passed

– Yes

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– No

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: no

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Eschaton was not a common concept in Chinese traditional thought. It emerged among a few Chinese Buddhist cults in the early medieval era. In their medieval Buddhist Apocrypha,

descriptions of various disasters in the Chen-Wei texts were introduced.

- ↳ At specified time in future
 - Yes
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - Yes
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - No
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes

- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: As politics was a major concern in the texts, warfare was mentioned quite often, but mostly in mysterious way.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– No

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

- ↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

- An empire

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

- No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

- No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

- Yes

- ↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?
– No

- ↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?
– No

- ↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?
– Hunting (including marine animals)

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

- No

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

- No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

- No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text

itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: As politics was a major concern in the texts, warfare was mentioned quite often, but mostly in mysterious way.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– No

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Hunting (including marine animals)

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